

STUDY ON EFFECT OF AGRICULTURE SOLID WASTE BAGASSE ASH AND GLASS FIBER ON BLACK COTTON SOIL

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Abstract: The growing cost of traditional stabilizing agents and the need for the economical utilization of industrial and agricultural wastes for beneficial engineering purposes has prompted an investigation into the stabilizing potential of bagasse ash in highly black cotton soil. This research work is aimed to evaluate the suitability of bagasse ash for stabilization of black cotton soil. Black cotton soil exhibits volume change behavior, resulting in significant uplift pressures and potential upheaval of structures, due to their high moisture content. Unfortunately, it is often impractical to completely prevent the presence of expansive soil in construction projects. Replacement or reinforcement of black cotton soil with alternative materials may not be feasible on a large scale. The black cotton soil (BCS) is classified as an expansive soil, requiring treatment for optimum stability. Through the addition of various materials, the black cotton soil can be effectively stabilized. In this study, sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA) was utilized as an admixture in concentrations ranging from 2.5% to 12.5% by weight in order to stabilize the black cotton soil. The liquid limit, plastic limit, plasticity index, standard proctor test, California bearing ratio and unconfined compressive strength tests were performed in laboratory to study the behavior of black cotton soil. This research article evaluates the impact of the addition of glass fiber on the strength characteristics of BCS. Glass fiber gains good properties such as rigidity, robustness, resistance and flexibility to chemical loss. Glass fiber is mixed with oven dried (2% to 8%) BCS by its weight. The geotechnical properties of the BCS sample are evaluated before and after treatment using various laboratory tests.

Keywords - Black Cotton Soil, California Bearing Ratio, Sugarcane Bagasse Ash, Glass Fiber Standard Proctor Test, Unconfined Compressive Strength Test

1. Introduction: The need to bring down the growing cost of soil stabilizers and the use of wastes for engineering purposes. The safe disposal of industrial and agricultural waste products demands urgent and cost effective solutions because of the debilitating effect of these materials on the environment and to the health hazards that these wastes constitute. In order to make deficient soils useful and meet geotechnical engineering design requirements researchers focused more on the use of potentially cost effective materials that are locally available from industrial and agricultural waste in order to improve the properties of deficient soils.

The over dependence on industrially manufactured soil improving additives (cement, lime etc.) have kept the cost of construction of stabilized road financially high. This has continued to deter the underdeveloped and poor nations of the world from providing accessible roads to meet the need of their rural dwellers who constitute large percentage of their population which are mostly rural farmers. Thus, the possible use of agricultural waste, such as bagasse ash, will considerably reduce the cost of

construction and as well as reduce or eliminate the environmental hazards caused by such waste. Bagasse ash is an agricultural waste obtained from milling of sugarcane.

black cotton soil occur in many parts of the world. However, the problem of expansion and shrinkage is associated with high moisture changes. Hence, it is restricted in areas where the seasonal variation in climatic condition is high. The large volume change with the periodic cycle of wetting and drying can cause extensive damages in civil engineering infrastructures; mainly on small buildings, shallow foundation and other lightly loaded structures including roads and airport pavements, pipelines etc.

2. Literature Review:

[1] K.S. Gandhi (2012) conducted research on enhancing the quality of subgrade soil by utilizing Bagasse ash. Bagasse ash has proven to be an effective method for drying wet soils and offering an initial increase in strength. This is particularly beneficial when constructing in areas with wet and unstable ground conditions. Several laboratory tests were carried out, varying the percentage of Bagasse ash from 0% to 10%. The results revealed a significant improvement in the engineering properties of the subgrade as the proportion of Bagasse ash in the soil sample increased.

[2] In a study conducted by Kiran R. G. et al. (2013), various proportions of bagasse ash and cement were mixed with black cotton soil. The researchers examined the impact of these mixtures on the strength parameters, specifically the CBR (California Bearing Ratio) and UCS cost of waste disposal has lead to intense global research towards economic utilization (Unconfined Compressive Strength). The results showed that the combination of bagasse ash and cement at different percentages had a significant effect on the values of MDD (Maximum Dry Density), CBR, and UCS. For instance, when 8% bagasse ash and 8% cement were added, the MDD values increased from 1.516 g/cc to 1.65 g/cc. Similarly, the CBR values increased from

2.12 to 5.43 when 4% bagasse ash was added with 8% cement. Additionally, the UCS values changed from 84.92 KN/m² to 174.91 KN/m² when 8% bagasse ash was combined with 8% cement.

[3] In their research, B.M. Patil et al. (2013) investigated the impact of Pond ash and RBI Grade 81 on the properties of the base course and subgrade soil for flexible pavements. They used locally available clayey soil as the subgrade and Grade III material for the base course. Various proportions were tested to determine the optimal mix. The addition of pond ash and RBI Grade 81 improved the soaked CBR value of the subgrade clayey soil and grade-III material, allowing for a reduction in road thickness

[4] In a separate study conducted by Jianhing Di et al. (2013), bituminous mixtures were tested using fly ash as a replacement for limestone mineral powder as filler. The researchers examined the effect of high temperature stability on bituminous concrete through rutting tests. Low calcium fly ash was utilized for this investigation. Six test samples were prepared with varying percentages (5%, 6%, and 7%) of filler material, which included limestone mineral powder and fly ash. The optimal bitumen content was determined using the Marshall Method. The dynamic stability, a measure of high temperature stability, increased from 27.4% to 30% as the quantity of fly ash was raised from 5% to 7%.

[5] M. Chittaranjan (2011) and colleagues employed agricultural residues like sugar cane bagasse ash, rice husk ash, and groundnut shell ash in the stabilization of the subgrade soil. Each waste material was applied separately at varying percentages of 0%, 3%, 6%, 9%, 12%, and 15%, followed by

conducting CBR tests for each percentage. The test outcomes indicated a rise in CBR value as the waste percentage increased, reaching an optimal content level.

[6] Amruta P. Kulkarni (2016) and team also conducted an experimental study on stabilizing black cotton soil using bagasse ash and lime. Their experiments showed that the plasticity index decreased and CBR value increased when the optimal ratio of bagasse ash to lime was utilized.

[7] The engineering properties of black cotton soil can be improved by the addition of sugarcane bagasse ash, as demonstrated by Ashish Murari et. Al (2015) . in their study. Through their experimental research, they found that the dry density and CBR value of the soil increased as the percentage of SCBA increased.

3. Methodology: In this chapter, the materials used and the methods adopted for the research are described with respect to their source.

3.1 Materials: The black cotton soil sample used for this research work is collected from duplex 3BHK row house near Hindustan textile market, Ozar, Nashik from one test pit. The soil is grayish black in colour highly plastic clay. A disturbed sample is collected from test pit at a depth below 1.5m in order to avoid the inclusion of organic matter

Waste bagasse ash as was obtained from pravara sugar factory which is located at Ahmadanagar Loni in Maharashtra in India. For this research, fresh bagasse ash is taken from the furnace cooled in air by applying a small quantity of water. Then, it is properly packed in sacks and transported to the laboratory. The glass fiber used in this study was purchased from the open market from authorized dealers in Nashik

3.2 Methods: Sample Preparation prior to treatment and testing, the sample was prepared in accordance with the method described in AASHTO T87-86. This method involves:

- air drying of samples and/or oven drying at 60°C or less;
- breaking up the soil aggregates by rubber covered mallet. Then, sieve analysis is performed to separate the dried soils into two groups. The first group involves preparing uniform samples for Atterberg limits tests. And the other for compaction and California bearing ratio tests.
- Then, soil and bagasse ash is mixed manually to get uniform mix ratio for each test.

Another solution to reinforce soil is by using fiber. It has been a solution to stabilize thin soil and localized repair of failed slopes. Unlikely geosynthetics, another reinforcement method using fibers is applied by distributing the fibers randomly. Fibers which can be used either natural fibers or synthetic fibers. Hejaz made a simple study by reviewing more than 100 researches of soil reinforcement by using natural and synthetic fibers. To prepare sample or specimens of fiber-reinforced soils to be tested in the laboratory, it can be mixed either manually or mechanically by using mixing machine.

Whatever the mixing method used, many researches implicitly assume that the fiber will be randomly distributed in the soil mass.

That orientation distribution would give the soil strength isotropy. Effects of fiber reinforced soil are relatively similar to geosynthetics reinforced soil for both coarse-grained and fine-grained soils, such as increasing bearing capacity and soil strength.

3.2.1 Advantages of Soil Reinforcement

1. Cheap, locally and widely available, ecofriendly.
2. It can enhance the soil strength.

3. It is not significantly affected by weather conditions, compared to cement, lime and other chemical stabilization techniques.

3.2.2 Disadvantages of soil Reinforcement

1. Despite the fact that many researches have been conducted to determine the effects of using fibers to improve the soil, there are still no scientific procedures or standard, especially for field project.

Results: This presents the results of laboratory tests and a discussion pertinent to the results. The relevant engineering property of the soil is evaluated both for natural and stabilized soil samples separately. The tests include Atterberg limits, moisture density relationship (compaction) and California bearing ratio (CBR). Atterberg’s limits, moisture density relationship (compaction) and CBR are conducted for uncured and 7 days cured soil samples.

The soil was found to be highly plastic expansive clay with low bearing capacity when it is soaked and high swelling potential and fell below the standard recommendations for most geotechnical construction works especially highway construction. Therefore, the soil requires initial modification and/or stabilization to improve its workability and engineering property.

Results that are related to swelling characteristics of the soil are also indicate that the soil is highly expansive clay with a free swell of about 210%, free swell index of 163.6 % and free swell ratio of 2.6. The soil has a maximum dry density of 1.26 g/cm³, optimum moisture content of 32.2 %, unsoaked CBR value of 15.5 % and soaked CBR value of 0.93 %. The results indicate pozzolanicity of the bagasse ash. The combined percent composition of silica, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ is more than 70%.

Table 1: Geotechnical properties of the soil

Property	Quantity
Liquid limit, %	54.89
Plastic limit, %	27.93
Shrinkage limit	52.23
Plasticity index, %	26.96
AASHTO soil classification	A -7- 5
Specific gravity	2.45
Maximum dry density, g/cm ³	1.53
Optimum moisture content, %	32.2
Soaked CBR value, %	3.91

Unsoaked CBR value, %	15.5
Colour	Grayish Black

3.3.1 Glass Fiber as stabilizer results

Glass fiber is a material consisting of numerous extremely fine fibers of glass. Size of glass fibers used are of 6 mm and 12 mm.

Table 2: Oxide Composition of Bagasse Ash

Constituents	% Composition
SiO ₂	60.98
Al ₂ O ₃	7.39
Fe ₂ O ₃	6.07
CaO	12.66
MgO	2.51
K ₂ O	3.53
Na ₂ O	0.15
P ₂ O ₅	0.61
SO ₃	1.23

The results indicate pozzolanicity of the Bagasse ash. The combined percent composition of silica, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ is more than 70%. The results of chemical tests carried out on bagasse ash are as shown in table 2.

3.3.1.1 Liquid Limit

The Casagrande’s Apparatus is used with tool cuts a groove of size 2 mm wide at the bottom and 11 mm wide at the top and 8 mm high. The number of blows used for the two soil samples to come in contact is not down as shown in Table 3 and Graph is plotted taking number of blows on a logarithmic scale on the abscissa and water content on the ordinate shown in Figure 1 Liquid limit corresponding to 25 blows only.

Table 3: Liquid Limit

No of Blows	Water Content (%)
28	53.80
33	51
34	59.88

Figure 1: Graph for Liquid limit for 25 blows

From the graph we obtained the liquid limit corresponding to 25 blows. Liquid limit is = 54.89%

3.3.1.2 Specific Gravity of the Soil

The specific gravity of soil is the ratio between the weight of the soil solids and weight of equal volume of water. It is measured by the help of a volumetric flask in a very simple experimental setup where the volume of the soil is found out and its weight is divided by the weight of equal volume of water. This test is carried out for two times as shown in Table 4 and the value was 2.45.

Table 4: Specific Gravity Calculations

Sample Number	1	2
Mass of empty bottle (M1) in gms.	112.45	115.27
Mass of bottle+ dry soil (M2) in gms.	163.83	165.27
Mass of bottle + dry soil + water (M3) in gms.	390.088	398.16

Mass of bottle + water (M4) in gms	359.448	367.87
specific gravity	2.4	2.5
Avg. specific gravity	2.45	

3.3.1.3 Plastic Limit

This is determined by rolling out soil till its diameter reaches approximately 3 mm and measuring water content for the soil, which crumbles on reaching this diameter. The detail of the test shown in Table.5 Plasticity index (Ip) was also calculated with the help of liquid limit and plastic limit;

Table 5: Plastic Limit

Mould	1	2	3
Wt. of container , W1 (gm)	8.8.	8.5	8.2
Wt. of container+ wet soil sample,W2 (gm)	15.3	14.4	15.5
Wt. of container+ dry soil sample,W3 (gm)	13.5	12.7	13.1
Water content (%)= $\{(W2-W3)/(W3-W1)\} * 100$	28.2	23.61	32
Plastic limit (mean value, %) = 27.93%			

$$IP = WL - WP = 54.89 - 27.93 = 26.96$$

So soil is high plasticity clay. It is also determine from the IS plasticity chart As per the plasticity chart we obtained that the soil is above A- line and CH or OH group. So soil is highly clay or high plasticity Liquid limit is = 54.89% plastic limit = 26.96% Plasticity index= 26.96

3.3.1.5 Standard Proctor Test

The soil sample is taken with fibers and baggase ash the standard proctor test is conducted. The details of the readings shown in Table 6. Soil sample taken: 6 KG Volume of mould used: 2650. 71cu.cm

Table 6: Standard Proctor Test Results

Description	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4
% of water added	6	10	14	18
Moisture content	6.66	12	25	36
Dry density	1.39	1.53	1.48	1.30

3.3 Conclusions: The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of the study/investigation carried out within the scope of the study.

1. The plasticity index slightly reduced with increased in bagasse ash content and curing has also an insignificant effect on the plasticity of the expansive soil.
2. The optimum moisture content increased while the maximum dry density values decreased with increment of bagasse ash content.
3. CBR values slightly increased with the addition of bagasse ash. The change in CBR value is not significant for both cured and uncured samples. Addition of bagasse ash alone does not improve the strength of soils due to presence of only reactive silica with low amount of calcium content in bagasse ash.
4. Mixing of soil with varying percentage of glass fiber lead to decrease in swelling behavior of soil and CBR value increases for soaked condition.
5. Mixing of soil with varying percentage of 6 mm Glass fibre to an increase in MDD and CBR value increases for soaked condition.

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